

ISic4332

I.Sicily inscription 4332

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact provenance unknown; seen by Libertini 'nel giardino Mancuso'
pre-1921.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334806

1. Κλωδίας

2. Πόλλας.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334806

Bibliography

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Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche
ed archeologiche. Florence. At 226 no.54

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